

TECHNICAL SUMMARY

Credit Scoring and Climate-Smart Agriculture

by Rishi Basak. Working paper, June 2017

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INTRODUCTION

Farmers in developing countries seeking loans are unfairly disadvantaged by screening models that overestimate risk of default – cutting them off from finance that could improve productivity and strengthen climate resilience. This study discusses the flaws in the current approach, showcases successful finance initiatives from around the world and presents opportunities to introduce climate-smart credit scoring that benefits farmers and banks alike.

WHAT IS CREDIT SCORING?

Credit evaluation is used to decide whether to lend and on what terms, for all types of loans:

- Mortgages
- Credit cards
- Car finance
- And agricultural credit.

But, without systematic screening it can be inconsistent - creating false perception of risk.

Financial institutions screen loan applications to reduce the risk of default. Applicants supply information and their current financial position and credit history are reviewed to determine the likelihood of any future transgression.

Those with low credit risk - strong financial position and good repayment history - are offered a loan. While those at the higher end of the scale are usually rejected.

However, loan screening in the developing world currently disadvantages small-holder farmers by overestimating default risk - especially if productivity is low and commodity prices uncertain.

Factor in concerns about extreme weather events, and requirements for approval become even more onerous, forcing farmers to turn to informal lending - the largest source of credit in many developing countries.

Credit scoring reduces subjectivity in the screening process and can bring additional benefits - such as

improved loan pricing.

It enables financial institutions to determine:

- Profitability
- Solvency
- Liquidity
- Repayment capacity

And account for other key factors, such as the sector and region in which the business operates.

Credit card companies have used these models for many years, but they're relatively new to microfinance.

Most small-holder farmers don't have reliable financial records, so their capacity to repay needs to be calculated using average costs, yields, market prices, and land for a given type of agricultural production. Risk determination must also account for qualitative factors related to farmers' equipment, irrigation, fertilization and use of pesticides, as well as skill level and track record.

Therefore, effective credit scoring for agriculture needs models that account for these unique characteristics.

HOW IS CLIMATE-SMART AGRICULTURE RELATED TO CREDIT SCORING?

Small-holder farmers denied access to credit are less resilient to climate change. And financial institutions that fail to consider its impact face increased risk exposure. Climate-smart credit-scoring incorporates climate risks (including climate-smart agriculture practices), when calculating creditworthiness.

Climate-smart agriculture (CSA) aims to sustainably:

1. Increase productivity
2. Make farming more resilient in the face of climate change
3. And reduce greenhouse gases from agricultural practices.

Goals that can be achieved by adopting CSA technologies and methods, such as:

- More efficient input
- Improved crop varieties
- And specialized machinery.

Which, in turn, lowers farmers' risk to lenders because CSA practices:

- Insure against adverse weather
- Minimize agricultural losses
- And increase revenues through enhanced productivity and higher prices achieved for better quality crops.

If credit scoring models incorporate the additional information below:

- Farmer's exposure to climate risk in terms of crop yields and quality
- The condition of the farm
- And the farming practices used, including specific CSA practices adopted.

Financial institutions can make better-informed lending decisions.

Differences between conventional credit scoring and credit scoring for climate-smart loans:

WHO IS SUCCESSFULLY IMPLEMENTING CREDIT SCORING?

A 2008 study found that most commercial lenders in Kenya, with the exception of international banks, weren't using credit scoring. Smaller lenders simply didn't have capacity to develop financial models in house.

This holds true across most developing countries - few organizations attempt to use credit scoring in the context of small-holder farm financing. And the initiatives that do exist have yet to integrate climate change considerations into their approach.

However, there are exceptions:

F3 Life is a social enterprise focused on climate-smart financing in Kenya. Participating farmers who adopt better agricultural practices qualify for

higher credit limits at lower interest rates.

The Agricultural Loan Evaluation System (ALES), developed by the Frankfurt School of Finance and Management, uses regional data to determine crop and region-specific farm financials to obtain credit scores. In Turkey three banks have successfully implemented the tool:

1. After testing, Akbank is preparing to use it in 28 provinces
2. Isbank is using the tool to score agricultural credit card applications
3. And Yapi Kredi Bank has implemented it in 250 branches since 2012.

The Frankfurt School of Finance and Management is adjusting credit scoring methods to include climate change considerations - applying the tool with microfinance institutions in Peru and Colombia as part of the Adaption project.

The project will provide microfinance to farmers adopting more sustainable practices that improve resilience to climate change. To date, more than 5,000 loans have been disbursed totaling US\$6.9 million, and almost 5,000 farmers trained.

In Kenya, FINA Bank, a small commercial bank focused on lending to SMEs, is using a data-driven approach to increase loans and credit to smaller businesses. The bank has equipped loan officers with laptops and a spreadsheet-based credit scoring tool, enabling them to improve efficiency of application, review and approval. It's hoped this approach will rapidly grow their small loan customer base, while reducing transaction costs and risk exposure.

The private sector is playing an increasing role in financing irrigation with individual farmers and collectives in countries like China and India eager to address sporadic surface water supply, better

manage water runoff, and gain control of their watering schedule driving demand for investment - an opportunity for local commercial banks to partner directly with governments in country-led initiatives.

OPPORTUNITIES FOR COMMERCIAL BANKS & OTHER FINANCIAL INSTITUTIONS

The benefits to financial institutions of using credit scoring include:

Faster and cheaper loan-making – automating risk assessment dramatically reduces time needed to approve/decline a loan - a significant cost saving

Increased volume of low-default loans – faster assessment means more loans can be processed

Ability to control portfolio risk – rich data on individual small-holder loan enables trend analysis by farmer type, location and other key criteria - enhancing control mechanisms at portfolio-level

Bias removal – credit scoring zeros in on relevant data, criteria and farmer characteristics that correlate with future credit performance. Arbitrary and non-evidence-based criteria and decision-making are eliminated

Better use of resources – credit scoring frees up resource, meaning loan officers can spend more time reviewing questionable loan requests, larger loans and existing loans threatening to become problematic.

CSA represents an opportunity for small-holder farmers to access finance and new, more productive technologies. Adoption of better practices reduces

risks traditionally associated with agricultural investment and can lead to the creation of carbon credits.

Measurement of farmers' risk and resilience, combined with climate-smart conditional lending, stands to benefit financial institutions and farmers alike. Commercial banks and other financial institutions reduce risk exposure, while farmers increase resilience, productivity and profit.

Lenders using climate-smart credit scoring gain access to data that can improve lending decisions by selecting farmers that are both credit worthy and climate resilient - reducing exposure to default and climate risk.

CASE STUDY - F3 LIFE

F3 Life is a Nairobi-based for-profit start-up providing climate-smart financial services to Kenyan farmers. Its Farmer's Life Service offers agricultural loans and technical farming advice packaged together. The cornerstone of F3 Life's climate-smart financing is its credit scoring system. Credit scores, interest rates and credit limits are contingent upon farmers' adoption of climate-smart agricultural, fishing and forestry practices, in addition to conventional credit criteria. The revenue generated by the interest charged on loans is used to fund technical assistance.

This approach aims to increase productivity of small-holder farmers, while promoting soil and water conservation, and improving watershed management. As farmers adopt conservation agriculture practices, soil erosion and water pollution are reduced, bringing longer term productivity benefits. This credit system also incentivizes farmers to continually improve. Loan conditions become more favorable as farmers

adopt sustainable farming practices - the most environmentally-friendly farmers benefit from the lowest interest rates. The advisory services provided by F3 Life also strengthen relationships with farmers - reducing risk of default.

Starter loans are offered at a monthly interest rate of 5% and begin at around US\$20. A streamlined conservation plan is included as part of the contract. Farmers can graduate to 'bronze status', gaining access to loans double the original amount, provided their initial loan is repaid within the repayment schedule; and there is evidence pre-agreed conservation measures are being adopted. Platinum clients can borrow as much as US\$225 and repay their loan over 12 months or more. After three loans are repaid according to the terms of the contract, a 2.5% monthly interest rate is unlocked. Loans are secured against the items purchased with the credit (i.e., farm equipment), as opposed to land title. Monthly inspections take place and farmers receive payment reminders via text messaging.

F3 Life uses microfinance software for the disbursement and repayment of loans - reducing transaction costs, as no cash is handled and loans can be tracked online. The software also records evidence of adoption of improved agricultural practices, as per the terms of the loan.

F3 Life hopes to reach 10,000 small-holder farmers by the end of 2017, with the ambitious goal of providing loans to 1,000,000 clients within the next decade. Additionally, the company plans to integrate further measures into its credit scoring and loan scheme, such as on-farm waste management and sustainable livestock management practices.

SOURCES: Buchner (2016); F3 Life (2016a, 2016).